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How to Evaluate Emerging Knowledge Infrastructures

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Scientific Organizers

- Anne Beaulieu, University of Groningen
- Christine Borgman, University of California, Los Angeles
- Sarah de Rijcke, Leiden University
- Kathleen Gregory, Leiden University
- Matthew Mayernik, University Corporation for Atmospheric Research, NSF

Workshop Report

Evaluating Emerging Knowledge Infrastructures: Learnings and Directions

Matthew Mayernik, Kathleen Gregory, Sarah de Rijcke, Christine L. Borgman and Anne Beaulieu
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Knowledge infrastructures are layered, spread out significant networks, and sometimes fuse, form bridges or fragment. Just like mushrooms. Photo by Damir Omerovic. Poster design: SuperNova Studios .NL

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Summary

This workshop, conducted in April 2024 and funded by the Lorentz Center at Leiden University and the Institute for Advanced Studies (IAS) at the University of Amsterdam, built on and expanded work done in two previous Knowledge Infrastructure (KI) workshops, held in 2012 and 2020¹. Twenty-two KI scholars and practitioners came together in Leiden, the Netherlands, to discuss and plan research directions. They explored how KIs that seek to support innovative forms of knowledge production can be evaluated in ways that go beyond methods of comparison. The key questions with which the workshop participants engaged included:

- What transitions are we seeing with regards to the core values of knowledge infrastructures?
- What are the social values that drive evaluation of infrastructures?
- Which implicit values (public/corporate) are embedded in knowledge infrastructures and how can they be identified?

The program included presentations, case study discussions, a talk series at IAS, and brainstorming and collaborative writing sessions. Across these activities, participants identified key themes and honed in on three focal areas for further development: KIs as part of enabling environments for citizen science; reconciling competing regimes of evaluation in knowledge infrastructures; and the sustainability of infrastructures as part of evaluation. The workshop also resulted in drafts and plans for three position papers to be followed by calls for special issues in relevant journals or book series in these three topical areas.

Photo 1. Most attendees, Lorentz Workshop on Evaluating Knowledge Infrastructures, April 2024

¹ Edwards, P. N., Jackson, S. J., Chalmers, M. K., Bowker, G. C., Borgman, C. L., Ribes, D., Burton, M., & Calvert, S. (2013). Knowledge infrastructures: Intellectual frameworks and research challenges (p. 40). University of Michigan. <http://hdl.handle.net/2027.42/97552>

Borgman, C. L., Darch, P. T., Pasquetto, I. V., & Wofford, M. F. (2020). Our knowledge of knowledge infrastructures: Lessons learned and future directions (Alfred P. Sloan Foundation). University of California, Los Angeles. <http://escholarship.org/uc/item/9rm6b7d4>

Workshop Background and Goals

Changing infrastructural and evaluation landscape

Science involves many kinds of evaluation, peer-review being the most ubiquitous form. Most contemporary approaches to evaluation focus on techniques of assessment, often through standardized comparison, whether to establish benchmarks or metrics, to develop rankings, or to provide evidence of outcomes. However, finding common ground for comparison between knowledge infrastructures—whether they serve scientific projects, function as facilities such as physical infrastructures like observatories, or digital platforms – is notoriously difficult because each entity is unique by design. In addition, when diversity and heterogeneity become important aspects of knowledge infrastructures², comparison seems an even less promising avenue. An important element in thinking about evaluation is therefore to examine how it is the result of both assessment practices and the values embedded in them. As some values become foregrounded (engagement rather than excellence, or access rather than performance), evaluation and assessment also need to change .

Need and form of new approaches to evaluation

In this workshop, we used the case of knowledge infrastructures that seek to support innovative forms of knowledge production —more often than not, unique resources—to explore the possibilities of evaluation beyond comparison. The term Knowledge infrastructure (KI) is a specific one that emphasizes how individuals and institutions, material research infrastructure components and skill sets to make, operate and extend those components are intertwined.³ It represents a comprehensive approach, and so encompasses what is often labeled as ‘research infrastructure’, itself a variable term⁴ often used in policy documents to indicate important resources for the knowledge production process:

“... facilities, resources and services that are used by the research communities to conduct research and foster innovation in their fields. They include: major scientific equipment (or sets of instruments), knowledge-based resources such as collections, archives and scientific data, e-infrastructures, such as data and computing systems and communication networks and any other tools that are essential to achieve excellence in research and innovation. They may be 'single-sited,' 'virtual' and 'distributed.’”⁵

We purposefully use the term *knowledge* infrastructures because it is more inclusive when it comes to describe the supporting elements/components for knowledge generation and circulation. KI is more inclusive along various dimensions; in particular it describes infrastructures beyond academia and outside strictly research-focused activities since it also

² Goldstein, J., & Nost, E. (Eds). (2022). *The Nature of Data: Infrastructures, Environments, Politics*. Lincoln, NE: University of Nebraska Press.

³ Edwards, Paul N., Ashley Carse, Robin Williams, Antti Silvast, Steven J Jackson, Christine Borgman, and Anne Beaulieu. 2024. “Infrastructures”. In *Elgar Encyclopedia of Science and Technology Studies*, edited by Ulrike Felt and Alan Irwin, 329–38. Cheltenham, UK: Edward Elgar Publishing.

⁴ Morselli, F. (2023) Co-creation dynamics in a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC). The case of the DARIAH-ERIC Working Groups. [PhD thesis, Università degli Studi di Verona]. <https://hdl.handle.net/11562/1115046>

⁵ Pg. 9 in; European Commission. (2015). *European charter for access to research infrastructures – Principles and guidelines for access and related services*, Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2777/524573>

includes teaching and training, and other kinds of users, such as indigenous or citizen science practitioners who are usually not included under the labels of “researcher” or of “scientific.”

Work on knowledge infrastructures of the past decade has made very important contributions to how we can understand how infrastructures are central to many crucial types of knowledge about climate change, human migration or biodiversity⁶. Nowadays, we have greater insight into the emergence, evolution, competition and coexistence among various types of infrastructures supporting diverse areas and topics of knowledge production. With this workshop, we wanted to foreground the relationship between those infrastructures, values that guide their design, the knowledge they sustain, and the role they play in the course of assessment. This wish is in line with recently expressed needs from those who are setting up and govern infrastructures⁷ and international bodies to reflect on and align infrastructure and assessment practices.

In sum, building on the scholarship on KI so far, which shows the entwinement of values and knowledge via infrastructures, we wanted the workshop to be the occasion to extend the analysis and reflection on the importance of values not only for design and epistemic consequences but also for modes of assessment.

Assessment of KIs poses particular challenges. KIs are rarely duplicated, by definition. They are expected to provide unique, stable, overarching solutions for knowledge production and to serve sometimes quite diverse communities efficiently. Yet, knowledge infrastructures are also (increasingly) themselves the object of assessment, whether formal or informal, as science is subject to increased demands for accountability⁸.

So far, knowledge infrastructures have usually been evaluated through bibliometrics - notably the number of resulting publications and citations, site visits, usage statistics like number of data downloads or researchers hosted, as well as analyses of their content coverage and comprehensiveness and the accessibility of their contents. However, as the aims of knowledge infrastructures change, these approaches may not be neither sufficient nor satisfactory⁹.

There are also significant shifts in the kinds of actors who provide infrastructures, and the institutional embedding and maintenance of knowledge infrastructures remains undervalued and unsupported, whereas this is a core component of sustainability¹⁰. Finally, infrastructures are also being put forward as part of evaluative work, for example in the form of 'research

⁶ Beaulieu, Anne. 2022. “Organising Knowledge for Sustainable Futures”. In *Handbook of the Anthropology of Technology*, edited by Maja Hojer Bruun, Dorthe Brogaard Kristensen, Rachel Douglas-Jones, Cathrine Hasse, Kalus Hoyer, Brit Ross Winthereik, and Ayo Wahlberg, 355–77. Palgrave.

Borgman, Christine L. 2007. *Scholarship in the Digital Age: Information, Infrastructure, and the Internet*. The MIT Press.

Edwards, Paul N. 2010. *A Vast Machine: Computer Models, Climate Data, and the Politics of Global Warming*. Cambridge, Massachusetts London, England: MIT Press.

Pelizza, Annalisa. 2023. “Securitizing the Infrastructural Europe, Infrastructuring a Securitized Europe”. In *Technopolitics and the Making of Europe*. Edited by Nina Klimburg-Wijtjes and Paul Trauttmansdorff, Routledge.

⁷ Tasovac, T., et al. (2023). The Role of Research Infrastructures in the Research Assessment Reform: A DARIAH Position Paper. <https://hal.science/hal-04136772/>

⁸ Mayernik, M. S., Hart, D. L., Maull, K. E., & Weber, N. M. (2016). Assessing and tracing the outcomes and impact of research infrastructures. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 68(6), 1341–1359. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.23721>

⁹ Lane, Julia. 2010. 'Let's Make Science Metrics More Scientific.' *Nature* 464 (7288): 488–89. <https://doi.org/10.1038/464488a>.

¹⁰ Plantin, Jean-Christophe. 2021. 'The Data Archive as Factory: Alienation and Resistance of Data Processors.' *Big Data & Society* 8 (1): 20539517211007510. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20539517211007510>

intelligence', in which third parties (commercial and non-profit) are developing data analytic services on and with large-scale infrastructures for research meta-data. What do such shifts and blind spots mean for evaluations of knowledge infrastructures?

Aims of the workshop

We see calls for reform of scholarly communication (open publishing, registration, data sharing) as well as of evaluation (Erkennen & Waarderen in the Netherlands¹¹, the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment¹²). In this workshop, we wanted to better understand how knowledge infrastructures are also subject to these trends and can contribute to such agendas for better assessment and evaluation practices.

As KIs continue to emerge and evolve, we also needed to think about how to assess them in ways that will help support their aims and allocate resources responsibly. While the evaluation of infrastructures has traditionally been aligned to values of access, efficiency and avoidance of redundancy, we saw important signs of change. The workshop was therefore especially timely because it helped to map out the transitions of knowledge infrastructures towards increasingly important values—openness, sustainability, epistemic diversity, democratization and participation. We therefore wanted to explore the possibilities for developing evaluation practices that are aligned to other emerging values. This will constitute an important contribution to the conceptualisation, practice, and policy of evaluation of knowledge infrastructures.

The Netherlands has a strong tradition of leading scholarship on evaluation and policy in science, a tradition we build on through involvement of scholars from key institutions (CWTS, Leiden University, SURF). In addition, there are a number of knowledge infrastructures based in the Netherlands that are explicitly seeking to develop in the context of transition mentioned above (ARISE in the area of biodiversity, Clariah and ODISSEI in social science and humanities and institutions such as DANS-KNAW or the eScience center supporting infrastructures). Most of these are connected to European and international efforts. Policy on knowledge infrastructures in the Netherlands but also in Europe and internationally (such as the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)) specifies the importance of accessibility, sustainability, and the FAIR principles. Interest in this space is further apparent in increasing funding streams for the development of research infrastructures¹³. So far, little attention has been paid to what this will actually mean for evaluation processes. The larger implications for the kinds of knowledge that such infrastructures can sustain has also been under-examined.

Ambitions and outcomes

To reach the aim to better understand how values and reform agendas affect knowledge infrastructures, we asked

- What kind of transition are we seeing with regards to the core values of knowledge infrastructures?
- What are the social values that drive evaluation of infrastructures?

¹¹ <https://www.nwo.nl/erkennen-en-waarderen>

¹² <https://sfedora.org/>

¹³ For example, the Dutch Research Council's Research Infrastructure funding scheme: <https://www.nwo.nl/en/calls/research-infrastructure-ri-national-consortia>

- Which implicit values (public/corporate) are embedded in knowledge infrastructures and how can they be identified?

To address the aim gaining insight into assessment of and with KI, we sought to

- develop a map of the changing landscape of KI that can be of use to developers, funders and users
- produce a constructive array of approaches to assessment of KIs, signaling the main values they reflect
- articulate how to rethink assessment to better reflect the changing values embedded in emerging knowledge infrastructures
- set out a path towards developing a working set of approaches and/or metrics to evaluate KI across multiple contexts

Workshop Design and Organization

This one-week workshop took place at the Lorentz Center at Leiden University from April 15- April 19, 2024. The planning for the workshop began much earlier, with the full team of organizers being assembled nearly one year in advance of the event. The organizational team consisted of:

- Prof. Dr. Anne Beaulieu, University of Groningen
- Prof. Dr. Christine Borgman, University of California, Los Angeles
- Prof. Dr. Sarah de Rijcke, Leiden University
- Dr. Kathleen Gregory, Leiden University
- Dr. Matthew Mayernik, University Corporation for Atmospheric Research, Boulder, CO

The workshop was designed to bring together both researchers as well as practitioners working at knowledge infrastructures (KIs) to engage in a series of talks, discussions, interactive brainstorming and writing about the topic of *evaluating emerging knowledge infrastructures*.

To this end, we structured the workshop to include discussions of three cases – emerging knowledge infrastructures of different types whom we invited to participate in the workshop. We did this with the goal of grounding our discussions, stimulating questions and interaction among the participants, and providing feedback to the KIs themselves. We asked each case to prepare a presentation describing, e.g. a short history of the infrastructure, the kinds of data and uses present, the main data flows, and their expectations, agreements, tensions or successes regarding evaluation. The presentations were followed by an hour of discussion and questioning. We organized a special session during the workshop to consolidate feedback to the case study members in order to ensure that participation was also useful to them.

In the run-up to the workshop, all participants were asked to submit a 1-2 page statement addressing all or some of the core issues of the workshop. The organizers provided the following prompts:

- In my experience (please specify), knowledge infrastructures are evaluated as follows:

- Knowledge infrastructures are especially important because... and because they support the following values:
- What kind of transition are we seeing with regards to the core values of knowledge infrastructures?
- When infrastructures are evaluated, these societal/public/corporate values are foregrounded.... Because...
- Which implicit values (societal/public/corporate) are embedded in knowledge infrastructures and how can they be identified?

The statements were shared with all participants ahead of the workshop. They were an effective way to get to know each other and to orient some of the sessions and group work for the week.

Workshop Description

This section summarizes the work and presentations from each day of the workshop.

Day 1: New values and emerging KIs

After an introductory round, we began with a discussion of five somewhat provocative positioning statements which were drawn from our individual reflections submitted in advance of the workshop. The afternoon sessions focused attention on the theme of the day by looking at our first case and a knowledge exchange session exploring the topic of “Doing Infrastructures Differently.”

Kasia Karpinska presented the case of ODISSEI, the Open Data Infrastructure for Social Science. She discussed the history and development of ODISSEI, as well as different modes of evaluation which are used at the infrastructure, including various metrics, knowledge performance indicators, and the ambition to evaluate social impact. Our discussions about the case centered on themes related to competition/collaboration with other research infrastructures, funding streams and sustainability, community definition/bounding, and questioning definitions of research infrastructures and knowledge infrastructures.

Stephanie Hobbis’ talk on “Infrastructuring Diverse Values: Beyond State- and Capital Centric Perspectives” highlighted the complex relationship between infrastructures and values, in particular how infrastructures materialize particular values, while excluding others. Based on research on very different Pacific islands (Lau islands in Solomon Islands and small islands off the coast of Vancouver Island), she provided insights into how, when and why particular infrastructures and their values (proliferation of state control and industrial-capitalist economies) are resisted, also through the creation and maintenance of alternative infrastructures for alternative values.

Jonathan Zurbach presented a thought-provoking critical exploration of persistent identifiers (PIDs) titled “Leveraging persistent identifiers in the transition of knowledge infrastructures towards emerging values.” In his talk Jonathan considered i) why we should pay attention to PIDs; ii) the possible approaches to be used and iii) the shifts in values which can be enacted

via PID implementation. Jonathan argued that PID implementation is “world making” (Tsing, 2005) and that not all PIDs enact the same values.

Across both presentations, the following themes were identified: Resistance, evolution and change of values over time; tensions between global and local contexts and what standards enable; activism (in more or less organized forms); tensions between corporate good and public good; and transience vs permanence.

Day 2: Current Issues in KI assessment & policy

To kick off the day, Sarah de Rijcke presented a talk titled “Valuing and evaluating KIs beyond comparison” and Matthew Mayernik presented “Evaluating KI via persistent identifiers: Conceptual and practical challenges.”

Sarah de Rijcke’s presentation detailed and contrasted two trends: i) the increasing demand for quantitative research metrics, which has become coupled with the growth of commercial infrastructures for research information and ii) the rise of responsible research assessment reforms focusing on rebalancing quantitative and qualitative methods of assessment. Through her analysis, she argued to move from ‘indicators to *indicating*’ as a way to enable generative, inclusive, and interactive evaluations.

Matthew Mayernik discussed a series of projects in which persistent identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) were assigned to data sets, software packages, computing systems, and research instruments and facilities. This talk outlined the main purposes of these efforts, including to track the scientific outcomes from the use of scientific resources, to enable scientific findings to be more reproducible, and to enable provenance connections between related resources. The talk also discussed key challenges in assigning PIDs to any type of resource, including the difficulties of defining boundaries around the resource of interest, and practical difficulties in incentivizing resource users to cite resources consistently and accurately.

After lunch, Margaret Gold introduced the topic of *citizen science* in the wider context of *Open Science*. Open Science is an inclusive construct aimed at combining various movements and practices, including the open engagement of societal actors. Citizen science can be viewed as one way to include non-professionals in scientific research. It is difficult to come up with one all-encompassing definition of citizen science, but the primary shared characteristic is the participation of societal actors in knowledge production in a non-professional capacity, and the underlying ethos of citizen science is described by a set of agreed upon it is often underpinned by similar principles developed by the community of practice. Margaret gave a brief glimpse of the plurality of citizen science by showcasing several wide-ranging CS projects that illustrate differing levels of engagement at varying stages of the research cycle. CS-projects may differ based on the level of engagement of citizen scientists, which can range from collecting and contributing data and knowledge to fully collaborative the full co-creation of research, and even entirely community-led research. In terms of infrastructure, contributory citizen science might be served by 'traditional knowledge / research infrastructures', while collaborative and community-led co-creation and participatory citizen science are part of “emergent knowledge / research infrastructures.”

Henri de Ruiter from the introduced a “Rijksinstituut voor Volksgezondheid en Milieu (RIVM) presented the “Samen Meten” case” and discussed the rise of citizen science sensor-based data gathering measurements within the context of national air quality monitoring. An important reason to start facilitating citizen science measurements for RIVM was the promise of better spatial and temporal resolution for air quality monitoring, as well as a potential positive business case. However, measuring air quality together with citizens also creates a context, or negotiation space, which might increase trust in the monitoring process. Therefore, evaluation of CS activities became more nuanced but also more complex. The current Samen Meten infrastructure supports citizen science initiatives but institutional requirements (firewall, security, corporate identity) make it difficult to fully engage in co-creation activities that require flexibility. Hence, participatory approaches might require a different knowledge infrastructure, or infrastructural elements.

The day ended with a trip to Amsterdam for an event at the Institute for Advanced Study (IAS) of the University of Amsterdam. The focal topic was “Good enough for what? How to evaluate knowledge infrastructures for citizen science.” Presentations by Dr. Paula Helm on language digitization in the Amazon and Dr. Carol Garzon Lopez on biodiversity monitoring in Latin America led to group discussion on how different values impact the development, use, and evaluation of knowledge infrastructures. Discussions ranged over various topics, including tools, indicators and evaluation protocols for citizen science, standards and their role within knowledge infrastructures, and approaches to data gathering to support knowledge for liveable futures.

Day 3: Aligning KI to new aspirations for research, evaluation and policy (I)

Katja Mayer spoke on “Differential Data Equity: Observations on Infrastructuring Participation in Citizen Social Science.” This talk discussed how evaluation of Citizen Social Science projects could be aimed at empowerment. In part, this would involve accounting for “differential data equity”. Data equity is not one universal norm, different needs and values may exist. This differential perspective is based on lessons learned from experiences with institutional review boards or informed consent procedures, the need for community building and co-creating representation, and finally taking into account the different impact pathways beyond the project end, but also “impact literacies” of involved actors. Thus the question is how to best integrate these learnings also into the evaluation? In the CoAct project the project partners experimented with the participatory design of the evaluation from the beginning of the project. “Co-Evaluation” was set up as a learning process, co-creating and re-visiting the project goals and data needs, when reflecting outcomes and outputs¹⁴.

Irene Pasquetto then spoke on “Science Opposition Infrastructures.” This talk discussed groups that make claims that are antithetical to claims in consensus science, namely anti-abortion science, creationist (anti-evolution) science, and climate change denialism science. These groups have organized processes to produce alternative claims. For such science opposition

¹⁴ Kieslinger, B., Schürz, S., Mayer, K., & Schaefer, T. (2022). Participatory evaluation practices in citizen social science: Insights from three case studies. *fteval Journal for Research and Technology Policy Evaluation*, 54: 10-19. <https://doi.org/10.22163/fteval.2022.567>

publics, the main goal is political, namely, to use evidence building to inform policymaking. Questions were raised about whether such science opposition groups should be characterized as “parasitic” in relation to mainstream science knowledge infrastructures¹⁵.

The next session involved the third workshop case study, which focused on the Open Research Knowledge Graph (ORKG). The ORKG motivation is that Systematic reviews and metaanalyses must make a huge effort to assemble information. The ORKG is a system in which findings and data presented in articles is extracted and restructured into a graph-based data structure, with the goal to allow linkages between scientific papers, findings, data, methods, techniques, places, and other entities, to be created, followed, and leveraged¹⁶. The current implementation covers only 30,000 papers and still requires manual augmentation of simple named entity recognition within the text. The goal is to expose the internal propositional structures within the papers in the form of structured statements that are amenable to machine-processing. These can be viewed as creating larger nano-publications. Unfortunately, the dynamics of the current system of scholarly communication mean that authors turn their arguments into text that then need to be parsed for consumption by machines, rather than authoring in an environment that could produce both human and machine-readable realizations. Questions emerged about what parts of knowledge production we need to do ourselves in order to still be able to think, to be creative, to be human beings. The emergence of knowledge graphs like ORKG also raise questions about the value of the conventional journal article and the functions of the scholarly record more generally¹⁷, as well as about the long-term maintenance of scholarly knowledge compiled in such graphs.

After a breakout session in which all three case studies were discussed via small groups, the participants reconvened to identify key topics for deeper discussion during the remaining workshop time. Participants individually wrote and discussed ideas via whiteboard/blackboard and shared documents, and performed a collective voting and sorting process to narrow down a wide set of topics to three. The day ended with an initial breakout of small group discussions of the selected topics. See section *Outcomes of Break-out Groups* below for details on the three topics selected for further development.

Day 4: Aligning KI to new aspirations for research, evaluation and policy (II)

Malcolm Campbell-Verduyn presented on “De/post-growth, accessibility and authority of knowledge.” His talk discussed issues related to knowledge infrastructure development and operation and growth (societal, economic, knowledge). The talk raised questions about whether KIs are re-inscribing injustices like colonialism, dichotomies about how growth is thought of and acted on, and gaps with other (knowledge) infrastructures? Anne Beaulieu then presented on “Revealing relations: From authoritative knowledge to assessable knowledge.” Her talk asked the key question, “why are we evaluating knowledge infrastructures?” Important topics in relation to this question include the criteria for evaluation, the purpose of the evaluation, the

¹⁵ Wofford, M. (2022). Parasitic Knowledge Infrastructures: Data Reuse by Anthropogenic Climate Change Skeptics. *Proceedings of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 59(1):837–839. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pra2.743>

¹⁶ Brack, A., Hoppe, A., Stocker, M., Auer, S., & Ewerth, R. (2022). Analysing the requirements for an Open Research Knowledge Graph: use cases, quality requirements, and construction strategies. *International Journal of Digital Libraries*, 23: 33–55. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00799-021-00306-x>

¹⁷ Van de Sompel, H., Payette, S., Erickson, J., Lagoze, C., & Warner, S. (2004). Rethinking Scholarly Communication. *D-Lib Magazine*, 10(9). <https://doi.org/10.1045/september2004-vandesompel>

logic of the assessment, and the way in which evaluations are performed. The talk also asked about the extent to which evaluations can or should enable a move from authoritative knowledge to assessable knowledge.

After these talks, the workshop participants broke out into sub-groups to continue work on the selected topics identified the previous day. Each group was tasked with sketching out a potential aim or outcome that could be pursued after the conclusion of the workshop, such as a proposal, white paper, or published article. The sub-groups then reconvened at the end of the day to discuss their ideas with the full group.

Day 5: Agenda-setting: Towards proposals for research, policy and assessment

On the final morning of the workshop, we collectively worked on this document, each participant contributing to their preferred section. We also populated a Zotero collection. This led to a highly concentrated working session followed by a reflection session that took the form of a plenary discussion and written feedback in a shared document.

Outcomes from the workshop

During a brainstorming session, we identified other emerging topics across talks and discussions, which were important outcomes of our conceptual work together. These topics were separate from the three focal areas which were addressed during the break-out groups. Some of these emerging topics were discussed and developed in more detail than others. In this section, we first present the topics that were discussed in the most depth, followed by briefer summaries of the ideas which were identified as being important but were not more fully developed during the workshop.

Distinguishing “Knowledge Infrastructures” from research, data, and information infrastructures: The utility of the concept

Paul Edwards, Malcolm Campbell-Verduyn, Anne Beaulieu

Most workshop contributors accepted the definition of KIs as “robust networks of people, artifacts, and institutions that routinely generate, share, and maintain specific knowledge about the human and natural worlds.”¹⁸ The original definition was directed at infrastructures designed to routinely produce *specific* knowledge, such as weather forecasts, labor statistics, or pandemic tracking. Previous work distinguished *systems* (centrally designed and controlled) from *networks* (similar systems, interconnected through standards or protocols) and webs or internetworks, often formed by disparate agents by joining resources belonging to different networks, with little or no centralized authority or control.¹⁹

¹⁸ Edwards, Paul N., *A Vast Machine: Computer Models, Climate Data, and the Politics of Global Warming* (MIT Press, 2010).

¹⁹ Edwards, Paul N., Steven J. Jackson, Geoffrey C. Bowker, and Cory P. Knobel. 'Understanding Infrastructure: Dynamics, Tensions, and Design,' January 2007. <http://deepblue.lib.umich.edu/handle/2027.42/49353>; Edwards, P. N., Jackson, S. J., Chalmers, M. K., Bowker, G. C., Borgman, C. L., Ribes, D., Burton, M., & Calvert, S. (2013) *Knowledge Infrastructures: Intellectual Frameworks and Research Challenges*. Ann Arbor: Deep Blue. <http://hdl.handle.net/2027.42/97552>; Edwards, P.N., 'Knowledge

We also looked at “An Agenda for Infrastructure Studies” from a 2009 *Journal of the Association of Information Systems* special issue that Paul Edwards co-edited to think about where we have come from and where we are now.²⁰ In 2009, the editors of the special issue noted that the concept of e-infrastructures captured several important changes: a move from individual computers and local networks to “distributed grid or cloud paradigms”; digital convergence of media/data processing/text with audio and video and images; and web-based interfaces. These marked a transition to what authors call “genuine” infrastructures (although there are still numerous standards, local structures are still the norm). What are the implications for evaluation of these knowledge infrastructures now (at that writing, evaluation was not on the radar)?

Although this special issue did distinguish among systems and e-infrastructures (among other terms we’ve discussed/used over the last week), in this workshop we did not strictly maintain these distinctions. Instead, under the “knowledge infrastructures” (KI) heading, we discussed a wide range of systems and networks that facilitate knowledge production or serve as elements of larger knowledge infrastructures. **Data or information infrastructures**, such as repositories (data) or libraries (information), support research work broadly. Some **research infrastructures** are more focused on supporting particular areas. ODISSEI is an excellent example; it created a network from pre-existing, unconnected systems and data resources widely used in the social sciences, such as demographic data, survey results, and statistics generated by government agencies, with the goal of making it easier for researchers to find and use any or all of them.

One utility of evaluating KIs lies in drawing out questions of *agency* (who acts, how, where, when? Also pointing to the agentic effects of how knowledge may be produced and circulated in ways that induce unexpected harms)²¹, as well as *values* in ways that may be more implicit in data or informational infrastructures. The *infra* of knowledge infrastructures allows for connection-making between (**very**) **broad claims about knowledge structures** (made by political economists about “neoliberalism,” or *the* knowledge structure²²) and **narrower focus on the technical dimensions of how research/information in knowledge infrastructures is encoded** (structuring data and related digital artifacts via standard formats, metadata, preservation policies, connections/federation with other systems, a coherent collection development policy, or via middle range theory²³).

Another key dimension is signaled by “infra”: the people whose often-invisible work maintains and repairs infrastructures, such as system operators, programmers, accountants, and hardware engineers. The former (knowledge structures, broadly understood) can overlap with

Infrastructures under Siege: Climate Data as Memory, Truce, and Target.' In *Data Politics: Worlds, Subjects, Rights*, edited by Didier Bigo, Engin Isin, and Evelyn Ruppert, New York: Routledge, 2019, pp. 21–42.

²⁰ Paul Edwards, Geoffrey Bowker, Steven Jackson, and Robin Williams, 'Introduction: An Agenda for Infrastructure Studies.' *Journal of the Association for Information Systems* 10, no. 5 (May 2009): 364–74. <https://doi.org/10.17705/1jais.00200>.

²¹ Eren, Selen, and Anne Beaulieu. 2023. “Between a Bird-in-the-Hand and Species Data in the Bank: Intermittent Care in Conservation Science”. *Theory, Culture & Society*, August, 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1177/02632764231187584>.

²² As understood by Strange (1988/1994b: 119) 'the' knowledge structure is 'what is believed (and the moral conclusions and principles derived from those beliefs); what is known and perceived as understood; and the channels by which beliefs, ideas, and knowledge are communicated— including some people and excluding others'. See also Haggart, B. and Tusikov, N., 2023. *The new knowledge: Information, data and the remaking of global power*. Rowman & Littlefield.

²³ Beaulieu, Anne, Andrea Scharnhorst, and Paul Wouters. 2007. “Not Another Case Study’: Ethnography, Formalisation and the Scope of Science”. *Science, Technology and Human Values* 32 (6): 672-692.

ideologies²⁴ while the latter may tend towards information infrastructures.²⁵ At the same time, infrastructure helps to maintain a focus on **structures** in ways that a focus on networks more specifically facilitates less, pointing at the widest to *disciplinary* or *professional* infrastructures such as the economics profession.²⁶ In this sense, knowledge infrastructures as a term is useful in pointing towards generation, sharing, and maintaining of specific knowledges that exist beyond institutions, or *in between* disciplines as the case of (green vs. de/post-)growth points to, specifically knowledge and policy contestations in battles between economists, ecologists etc on how to use and develop finite planetary resources. A utility of focusing on KIs then is to inform *inter-, intra-* and *trans-disciplinary* debates with attention to the reproduction of research agendas and policy relevance, and more generally of agency and related issues of power, legitimacy and authority.

Interrogating functions of “community” or “stakeholders” in setting out value of KIs

Kathleen Gregory, Louise Bezuidenhout

The notion of communities permeates discussions about knowledge infrastructures and their components. Research infrastructures are developed in response to the needs of their designated communities. Similarly, appeals to the utility for the community are a common justification in funding applications. Despite this, the notion of communities often remains vaguely defined or is conceptualized and operationalized in often reductive ways. e.g. by measuring the number of people visiting a website. The idea of community engagement can also be reductive, where speaking with a handful of individuals can be used as a signifier of interacting with and building on the needs of a broader “community.”

There are different models of conceptualizing communities and community building that emerged in our discussions of cases; these different models affect modes of evaluating KIs. We discussed the “build it and they will come” model, where a KI is built with a vague definition of a community and very often was not taken up or integrated into daily life and work. This contrasted with other examples (e.g. in the case of ODISSEI or DARIAH), where a KI emerged from and was developed with community members to address specific problems. These infrastructures continue to be woven into the work of researchers, even as the infrastructures expand.

The governance and organizational structures of KIs are also a key element of the community discussion. Who has a voice in making decisions about the direction of the infrastructure? Which communities are represented in governance decisions and which are not? Such considerations lead to the question of whose community is it really? Infrastructures speak about 'our community' – but do people actually identify as being a member of the infrastructure's community? We find it more likely that individuals identify as members of other communities,

²⁴ Tooze, R., 2018. Ideology, knowledge and power in international relations and international political economy. In *Strange Power* (pp. 197-216).

²⁵ Hanseth, O., Monteiro, E. and Hatling, M., 1996. Developing information infrastructure: The tension between standardization and flexibility. *Science, Technology, & Human Values*, 21(4), pp.407-426.

²⁶ See literature on knowledge networks e.g. Stone, D. 2013. “Shades of Grey”: The World Bank, Knowledge Networks and Linked Ecologies of Academic Engagement. *Global Networks* 13 (2): 241–60; Young, B. and Scherrer, C. eds., 2010. *Gender knowledge and knowledge networks in international political economy* (pp. 1-23). Baden-Baden.

and the KI is just one element of their own sociotechnical network of community formation – an element that enables people to come together and get on with doing what they care about.

These interlinking discussions highlight the need for more precise definitions of communities in relation to KIs. Absence of careful consideration of how the term is used impacts fundamental aspects of KIs, such as design, justification, impact and long-term sustainability. Other words such as “stakeholders” and “users” are also discussed alongside “communities.” Each of these words does its own type of work and deserves deeper interrogation. The notion of “communities” in particular seems warm and fuzzy, but are there other sides to this idea?

Meta question: why evaluate KIs?

Matthew Mayernik, Kathleen Gregory

Why would any given KI be subject to evaluation? Evaluation is a component of a broader assessment culture, which is itself tied to values embedded within assessment practices and within infrastructures themselves. Which forms of evaluation are best aligned with emerging values, such as openness, sustainability, equity, epistemic diversity, democratisation and participation? What actually needs to be evaluated, for which purposes and by whom?

Considering such questions is critical to any form of evaluation. We discussed a few (of many possible) motivations behind evaluating knowledge infrastructures. Some are economically driven, e.g. to prove a return on investment or demonstrate value to funders and stakeholders (as in the case of ODISSEI) or to obtain new or continued funding streams. Other motivations for assessing infrastructures could be related to the broader “evaluation culture” which exists within academia, but also outside of academia, e.g. in industry or user-centered design. Here, evaluation is an expected part of a workflow, even if it is not particularly well thought out.

Image 2 shows a drawing by Andrew Treloar from the first day of the workshop. The drawing depicts a number of considerations related to evaluation of KIs. The bottom right shows motivations noted in the previous paragraph, namely, to assess the impact and outcomes of a given KI, the value of the dollars spent to build it, and a general “just because” motivation that might encompass other reasons for evaluation. Beyond this “why,” however, the drawing shows considerations related to how an assessment might be done, namely, what criteria, values and theoretical assumptions an evaluation might have. Further, evaluations of KIs might focus on different components, such as their containers, contents, or systems. And underneath all of this is a question about who might be doing an evaluation of a KI. Evaluations done by users, builders, or funders might all lead to different outcomes depending on the “what,” “how,” and “why” considerations.

Image 2 - Drawing by Andrew Treloar

In a presentation on day four of the workshop, Anne Beaulieu also discussed similar questions of how and why to perform KI evaluations. She noted that evaluations can be formal or informal, and also might be one-time events, cyclical (such as annual evaluations), or tied into everyday operations of the KI. The logic of assessment is another important consideration. Are evaluations being done to assess outcomes, internal coherence of a KI, or to compare/benchmark one KI against others? The criteria for success of a KI vary accordingly. Success indicators for KIs might be the quality/quantity of their output, while for other KIs more important indicators might be their role in contributing to change of specific cultures or practices, or in engendering certain types of use and contribution from particular groups of people. Anne's comments reflected discussions that took place throughout the workshop on these considerations, and highlighted how the purpose of evaluation is typically multi-faceted, as evaluation may take place for a number of reasons: for funding, for legitimacy, for trust in resource, for engagement/commitment/participation, and for learning.

The value of training and guiding reviewers

Paul Edwards

Reviewers of knowledge infrastructures need some understanding of the goals and purposes of such systems – especially when no specific knowledge production outcome is envisaged, as in the case of research or data infrastructures. It may be useful to provide historical background, such as the constraints faced by previous generations of researchers in collecting data or finding relevant information, and how the infrastructure under review has changed those constraints. In many cases some of the greatest achievements of new infrastructures lie in the ways they connect pre-existing resources or systems. This task can be monumentally difficult – yet if successful, it results in seamless interoperability, potentially underappreciated by

reviewers. Explicating the concept of 'infrastructure' itself can help evaluators understand the value of these systems and services.

Use cases as effective way to demonstrate the value of infrastructure

Matthew Mayernik

As described above, evaluations must be directed by a purpose, with evaluative measures or indicators that are targeted according to the purpose. With this in mind, discussing evaluation of KIs is helped by focusing on specific cases. Cases can be useful to illustrate the evaluative trajectory for particular KIs, from conception of the evaluation to operationalization and execution. If infrastructures themselves have been designed with specific use cases in mind, such as particular scientific questions or tasks to be supported²⁷, these can be used as a starting point to guide an evaluation. But each KI may have other specific characteristics that are important to account for within an evaluation. Case-focused research has its own limitations²⁸, however. Aggregating and comparing multiple cases is important, as is being attentive to the idiosyncrasies of any specific case. But cases provide an important lens through which evaluation can be studied and improved.

Unintended or undesirable outcomes of openness

One of the issues raised was navigating the tensions between what is made 'open' and when/how and what/when "closure" is necessary to avoid/minimize harm (in other words, when 'emergence' can/should/ought to end). This contributes to the issue of agency. Examples include indigenous languages - not all stakeholders wanted to share their knowledge in the particular way that the knowledge infrastructure demanded. Another example from Kalpana Shankar's current work is the tension between open science mandates and commercialization drivers in public-private research partnerships. Funding mandates may require openness but tech transfer offices at universities will support commercialisation where possible. How do these tensions become embedded (or translated) into knowledge infrastructures is an open question. A further example comes from blockchain or hacker worlds ("information wants to be free") where knowledge facilitating the identification of persons like whistleblowers can generate harms, but also reduce harms (e.g when applications of such technologies are used for money laundering, terrorism finance etc).

Outcomes of break out groups on focal topics

This section summarizes the work done in the break-out groups on Days 4 and 5 of the workshop on three key topics: knowledge infrastructures in citizen science; evaluating the sustainability of knowledge infrastructures; and reconciling competing evaluation regimes in knowledge infrastructures.

²⁷ Fox, P., McGuinness, D. L., Cinquini, L., West, P., Garcia, J., Benedict, J. L., & Middleton, D. (2009). Ontology-supported scientific data frameworks: The Virtual Solar-Terrestrial Observatory experience. *Computers & Geosciences* 35(4), 724–738. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cageo.2007.12.019>

²⁸ Beaulieu, A., Scharnhorst, A., & Wouters, P. (2007). Not another case study: A middle-range interrogation of ethnographic case studies in the exploration of e-science. *Science, Technology, & Human Values* 32.6: 672-692. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0162243907306188>

Group 1: KIs as part of enabling environments for citizen science

Irene Pasquetto, Katja Mayer, Margaret Gold, Henri de Ruyter, Markus Stocker

As the scientific infrastructure becomes increasingly open, public participation in processes of knowledge production is not only desirable, but there is also a growing field of practice bridging the divide between science and society. Still, little is known about the multiple ways in which formal knowledge infrastructures and participatory research initiatives can exist in relation to each other. These relationships can take many forms depending on the domain of research, and the infrastructure configurations can also vary widely based on the underlying needs and context. There are cases in which knowledge infrastructures and citizen science initiatives operate as independent entities, for example in the case of government-led knowledge infrastructures that collect official air quality data such as the Dutch National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM) monitoring of particulate matter and nitrogen dioxide) and local community-based air quality monitoring initiatives that use low-cost sensors to track air quality and report local sources of air pollution independently (such as the data shared on the Sensor Community platform) In other instances, participatory research initiatives can be integrated into existing knowledge infrastructures as local systems (such as biodiversity data on the Global Biodiversity Index Facility (GBIF), of which a significant proportion is citizen-gathered data), or even participate in the co-creation of an infrastructure that is co-designed and then adopted by both experts and non-experts communities (such as the Integrated Marine Debris Observing System that incorporates both formal and citizen-gathered data into one infrastructure). In all of these cases, questions arise on how data collection methods can and should be standardized, how resulting outcomes should be evaluated, and how outcomes can be informative for citizens, scientists, and other stakeholders (such as policy makers). Based on these reflections, we pose the following questions to the research community:

- What types of knowledge flows happen in such infrastructures?
- What are the various forms of relationships that can exist between different types of participants and knowledge infrastructures, and how do these relationships evolve?
- What are the benefits and challenges of integrating public participation in knowledge infrastructures within the realm of citizen science?
- What policy changes are recommended to foster healthier, more productive interactions between public participation actors and knowledge infrastructures?
- What are the unintended/ undesirable outcomes of co-creation via KIs? (risks of paternalism, extractivism, manipulation)
- How can knowledge infrastructures be designed to empower rather than marginalize public contributors, particularly in the context of citizen science?
- In what ways can the design of knowledge infrastructures either replicate or mitigate existing power dynamics between the public and the other stakeholders?
 - How robust are they to non-intended usage?
 - How do you negotiate contradictory outcomes?

These research questions will also be raised in the planned outcomes from the group. Outcomes planned are a discussion paper and following on that a special issue in an interdisciplinary journal on KIs as enabling environments for Citizen Science. The discussion paper aims at opening up a scientific reflection on the necessary elements of KIs for societal transformation. Its objective is to map the still not connected well enough discourses on and experiences with public participation in science and policy with the question of infrastructures for knowledge production. After a delineation of the areas of interest: public participation - knowledge infrastructures - citizen science, the paper will explore diverse modalities of

engagement and typologies of infrastructures that either reinforce or challenge existing power relationships within knowledge production. The paper will also point to the fact that knowledge is not a stable category, instead that it should be the focus to understand the different functionalities and indeed the different knowledges involved.

The paper argues for the critical examination of “boundary organisation” and “different stacks” in knowledge infrastructures — and their different effects on knowledge production and participation — their alignment with or divergence from desired outcomes in KIs. It highlights the importance of robustness of KIs and the design of participation as a thematic pillar, essential for enhancing the resilience of KIs while ensuring that they remain responsive and inclusive of public inputs aiming at societal transformation. The concept of “negotiation spaces” is introduced where new layers or types of knowledge are co-created, fostering novel roles and responsibilities among participants.

In positioning this discussion within the scope of a proposed special issue, our paper aims to set the stage for further empirical and theoretical development that will elucidate emergent relationships between public participation and KIs. Here the objective is to create deeper understanding of how the “making of publics” in public participation in KIs are co-shaping our knowledge about the worlds we live in, our understanding of the infrastructuring of power, and the co-creation of more liveable futures.

Group 2: Reconciling competing regimes of evaluations in KIs

Anne Beaulieu, Andrew Hoffman, Stephanie Hobbis, Selen Eren

This group set out to discuss to what extent, how (and if at all), it may be possible to reconcile competing regimes - or modes - of evaluations in knowledge infrastructures. In this attempt, we variously discussed iterations of the following guiding question: “To what extent/how is it possible to enable different modes of evaluation for different outcomes?”

This guiding question required us to define and discuss both what we mean by 'different outcomes' and by “different modes of evaluation.”

Problematization: What makes this question relevant? Why are we asking this now?

- Increased diversity of knowledge actors (for ex. citizen science) and of the kinds of practices and outcomes that are relevant to different actors
- Increased demand for actionable outcomes within and for different scales (e.g. time and place) than those of peer-reviewed journal articles.
- More attention to more-than-humans, to nature as part of infrastructures
- Increasing diversity of contributors and stakeholders (with related needs for better interfaces, etc)
- Range of proprietary modes that affect circulation (open science; replication or registration requirements; security) that are based on different kinds of valuation

In our discussion of “**different outcomes**” we questioned if/when/how the growing complexity of societal and scientific grand challenges, like climate change and biodiversity loss, requires - and enables - synthesizing not just heterogeneous data types and knowledge sources, but also

for integrating the many communities that responsibly steward these resources – and which function as the critical “human infrastructure”²⁹ that enables their interleaving. Such human infrastructure itself continues to diversify, involving not just scientists, policymakers, and other technical experts, but also experts of experience – the individuals and groups who are already, or who stand to be, affected by the large-scale socio-ecological transformations we are currently witnessing. In other words, our capacity to make sense of, and to intervene upon, these challenges demands robust *knowledge infrastructures* (KIs) that can meaningfully draw together³⁰ “networks of people, artifacts, and institutions” to these ends.³¹

Based on this, and additional reflections, we identified two interlinked aspired 'different outcomes': (1) overarching goals/visions (the underlying purpose of KIs) at different scales of time and place, for example; a KI for transforming landscapes for multispecies liveable futures in the long term and a KI for preventing the loss of X species by Y time, (2) the KIs themselves – both *in toto*, and their individual constituent components, more concretely including outcomes such as experiment protocols, collective experiments, and emergent management recommendations. Knowledge infrastructures are indeed an outcome rather than a starting point: it is only through processes of *infrastructuring* that these networks ultimately accrete and sink into the background, forming the more or less invisible basis for the work of knowledge production and world-making that they enable.

We, thus, proceeded - in a non-linear fashion – to ask how these “different outcomes” may be subjected to evaluation: at different *moments in time*, by different *actors*, for different *purposes*, and according to different *modes, conventions, and metrics*; and in different scales extending not only to the technical systems like databases, knowledge bases, repositories, or research infrastructures that KIs bring into their fold, but extends also to the *human* actors who build, use, or otherwise engage with them, and to the *governance mechanisms* and *work practices* that coordinate their development, maintenance, extension, and (re)use.

In view of struggles to achieve different outcomes with current modes of evaluation, we then discussed possibilities for “**different modes**” of evaluation. A diversifying ecology of evaluative practices poses new challenges for policymakers, funders, researchers, and the many other communities (however defined) who contribute to, use, or are otherwise interpolated through KIs insofar as the meaningfulness of any given evaluation is a function of its (appropriate) proximity to the object or subject of evaluation during a given evaluative moment.³² The challenge, then, is one of establishing *gateways*³³ that facilitate and preserve the function, utility, and meaning of evaluation at the moment and scale where it is most meaningful, while also enabling such evaluative outcomes to be *legible* during other moments – involving other

²⁹ Lee, C. P., Dourish, P., & Mark, G. (2006). The human infrastructure of cyberinfrastructure. *Proceedings of the 2006 20th Anniversary Conference on Computer Supported Cooperative Work*, 483–492. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1180875.1180950>

Hobbis, S.K. and Hobbis, G. (2022) 'Non-/human infrastructures and digital gifts: The cables, waves and brokers of Solomon Islands internet', *Ethnos*, 87(5): 851–873.

³⁰ Botero, A., Karasti, H., Saad-Sulonen, J., Geirbo, C. G., Baker, K. S., Parmiggiani, E., & Marttila, S. (2019). *Drawing Together, Infrastructuring and Politics for Participatory Design*. University of Oulu, Finland. <https://hdl.handle.net/2142/103012>

³¹ Edwards, P. N., Jackson, S. J., Chalmers, M. K., Bowker, G. C., Borgman, C. L., Ribes, D., Burton, M., & Calvert, S. (2013). *Knowledge Infrastructures: Intellectual Frameworks and Research Challenges*. <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/2mt6j2mh>

³² cf. Antal, A. B., Hutter, M., & Stark, D. (2015). *Moments of Valuation: Exploring Sites of Dissonance*. Oxford University Press.

³³ Egyedi, T. (2001). Infrastructure flexibility created by standardized gateways: The cases of XML and the ISO container. *Knowledge, Technology & Policy*, 14(3), 41–54. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12130-001-1015-4>

components of the KI, and possibly other modes of evaluation – and ideally to be *interoperable* with them as well.

Developing mechanisms and recommendations for preserving evaluative relevance across KIs means first understanding the contours of any given KI and the expected moments and modes of evaluation that actors expect to encounter through their engagements with KIs. To this end, we propose to develop an initial approach for 'drawing together' the constituents parts of KIs and for carrying out a “participatory mapping” exercise during which the relevant actors are asked to map out (1) which parts of the KI they expect or wish to evaluate, as well as the expected or desired (2) temporality of these evaluations, (3) mode of evaluation that will be undertaken therein, and (4) actors to be directly involved or otherwise implicated in the evaluation.

Central to such a “different mode of evaluation” is that it attempts to avoid asking “leading questions” by focusing the minds of those being evaluated/contributing to the evaluation on particular indicators rather than on the broader vision of their work and KI. Hence, we discussed how initial discussions/drawing/mapping exercise focus on teasing out how involved actors envision, in drawing, both the “big picture” (what they seek to achieve, facilitated, at least in parts, by their KI/s) and, subsequently, how they envision (experience the current iteration of) their KI/s. Only after this broader reflection, the evaluation could and perhaps should - as a means of translation between different modes and goals of evaluations - to a more detailed discussion e.g. of indicators as set out at the beginning of a project and/or by funders. Such indicators may involve considerations such as effectivity in achieving its initial aims, leading to unexpected value creation, building new multispecies relations and capacities, and self-reflexivity on the aims, outcomes, and the process. The structure of the evaluation then loops back to the need for gateways that enable complex evaluations of complex objects without (extensive and/or purposeful) atomization of these objects.

Group 3: Sustainability of infrastructures as part of evaluation – funding, personnel, software, “communities”

Andrew Treloar, Kathleen Gregory, Kalpana Shankar, Jonathan Zurbach

This group spent some time discussing a rich cluster of issues relating to sustainability, as well as the most useful output to come from this workshop. One of the drivers of this work was a recognition of the increase in knowledge infrastructures (both in kind and number) over the last 15 years, as well as an increase in reflections on/analyses of these infrastructures. After a very useful discussion about what would add the most value to the field, it was agreed to focus on the role of evaluation (broadly construed) in aiding the sustainability of knowledge infrastructures over time, both in terms of their impact on the research ecosystem, and their long-term viability. Evaluation was scoped down to self-evaluation (not external evaluation) and a number of critical questions for such a self-evaluation were identified: what would success look like, is growth a necessary assumption, who is driving the evaluation and how might the strategy need to change over time. The word 'emerging' triggered a discussion about infrastructure lifecycles, and how different sustainability concerns would be most relevant at different stages in the lifecycle. Finally, a number of possible dimensions to structure the self-evaluation were identified. These dimensions would be used to strengthen the long-term viability

of an infrastructure over time, rather than assess its efficacy at a specific time point. Identifying what these dimensions are will continue to be discussed by the group after the workshop, and will be guided by relevant frameworks such as the Global Open Research Commons typology³⁴, the CoreTrustSeal criteria³⁵, and the nine-dimensional framework from Eschenfelder et al³⁶. The most likely output from this group will be a position paper to be submitted to a digital curation journal.

Links to prior KI workshops

Matthew Mayernik

This workshop has antecedents in two KI-focused workshops that took place in 2012 and 2020 respectively. The reports from these prior workshops demonstrate the foundations and growth of the knowledge base around KIs. Here we highlight some key points of trajectory of thought and focus from the prior workshops to our most recent meeting.

2012³⁷ - The first KI-focused workshop provided insight into key foundational questions of what KIs are, why they are important to contemporary scholarly and society, and their key characteristics. Evaluation was not a focus of this report or of the research on KIs at this point. The report noted a few evaluation questions for KIs, such as how to evaluate their contents (e.g. data quality) or the work that they enable. But there is no discussion of evaluation of KIs themselves. The report's conclusion does provide a reminder "that infrastructural change normally takes decades rather than years, and that very substantial social learning must take place before the full benefits of new sociotechnical systems can manifest" (pg. 24). This is an implicit acknowledgement that evaluation will be a necessary and important consideration going forward.

2020³⁸ - The second KI-focused workshop built explicitly on the first workshop, with a focus on tracking growth and evolution in KI research. This report characterized lessons learned from KI-focused research up to that point and identified a forward-looking KI research agenda. A key theme of the 2020 workshop was to characterize how KIs are changing. This demonstrates a next step within the research field since the 2012 workshop, which established KIs as a key concern for socio-technical research fields. The 2020 workshop provided a benchmark of progress and changes, both of KIs themselves and of research on their uses, characteristics, and outcomes. Like the 2012 workshop report, however, this 2020 workshop report also has no explicit discussion of evaluation of KIs.

2024 - This third workshop thus demonstrates a trajectory that builds on the prior two. If evaluation was not a focus of the prior workshops, it was because the KI concept and research

³⁴ Treloar, A., & Woodford, C. J. (2024). Global Open Research Commons: Creating an International Model for Improved Interoperability and Collaboration. *Data Science Journal*, 23: 56. <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2024-056>

³⁵ <https://www.coretrustseal.org/>

³⁶ Eschenfelder, K. R., Shankar, K., Williams, R. D., Salo, D., Zhang, M., & Langham, A. (2019). A nine dimensional framework for digital cultural heritage organizational sustainability. *Online Information Review*, 43(2): 182–196. <https://doi.org/10.1108/oir-11-2017-0318>

³⁷ Edwards, P. N., Jackson, S. J., Chalmers, M. K., Bowker, G. C., Borgman, C. L., Ribes, D., Burton, M., & Calvert, S. (2013). *Knowledge infrastructures: Intellectual frameworks and research challenges* (p. 40). University of Michigan. <http://hdl.handle.net/2027.42/97552>

³⁸ Borgman, C. L., Darch, P. T., Pasquetto, I. V., & Wofford, M. F. (2020). *Our knowledge of knowledge infrastructures: Lessons learned and future directions* (Alfred P. Sloan Foundation). University of California, Los Angeles. <http://escholarship.org/uc/item/9rm6b7d4>

field was itself still nascent and focused on more fundamental concerns. By 2024, however, KIs are themselves growing in scope, number, and designated communities. Many governments and other institutions have invested considerable resources and funds into building, operating, and maintaining KIs. The KI research community has itself also grown, with studies of many KIs of different types and sizes. As such, evaluation is now a ripe topic for deeper investigation. This workshop also demonstrates continued evolution in the kinds of disciplines where KI resonates and/or is used. At a more detailed level, this workshop did touch on a few specific topics that were also discussed in reports from the prior workshops. As one example, sustainability of KIs is a focus that has recurred across all three workshops. This workshop did feature new topics, however, such as the focus on ecological concerns. This was not part of earlier workshop discussions.

It should be noted here that all three of these workshops themselves build on a 2007 workshop and report that focused on the more general concept of “infrastructure.” Evaluation is discussed explicitly in a few places in the 2007 workshop report, including in one of the core recommendations. This is captured in the report’s executive summary as follows:

“By applying well-understood evaluation tools, we can assess and compare existing cyberinfrastructure projects, both in the US and abroad. The resulting knowledge can be used to improve reporting mechanisms and incentive structures. Cyberinfrastructure projects can also be instrumented to collect social and organizational data.”³⁹

Thus, our 2024 workshop represents a deep dive into a topic that is key for the success of infrastructure building efforts, but has not been a central focus in other topical workshops.

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Workshop Participants

Name	Affiliation
Anne Beaulieu	Department of Knowledge Infrastructures, University of Groningen
Louise Bezuidenhout	CWTS, Leiden University
Christine Borgman	Department of Information Studies, University of California, Los Angeles
Malcolm Campbell-Verduyn	Department of International Relations and International Organization, University of Groningen
Sarah de Rijcke	CWTS, Leiden University
Henri De Ruyter	RIVM - National Institute for Public Health and the Environment, Netherlands

³⁹ Pg. ii in: Edwards, P.N., Jackson, S.J., Bowker, G.C., & Knobel, C.P. (2007). *Understanding Infrastructure: Dynamics, Tensions, and Design*. Ann Arbor: Deep Blue. <http://pne.people.si.umich.edu/PDF/ui.pdf>

Paul Edwards	Program in Science, Technology & Society (STS), Stanford University
Selen Eren	Cultural Anthropology Research Unit , University of Oulu
Margaret Gold	Citizen Science Lab, Leiden University
Kathleen Gregory	CWTS, Leiden University
Stephanie Hobbis	Wageningen University
Andrew Hoffman	CWTS & CADS, Leiden University
Kasia Karpinska	ODISSEI - Open Data Infrastructure for Social Science and Economic Innovations
Katja Mayer	Science and Technology Studies, University of Vienna Center for Social Innovation, ZSI, Vienna
Matthew Mayernik	NSF National Center for Atmospheric Research
Irene Pasquetto	College of Information, University of Maryland
Andrea Scharnhorst	DANS
Kalpana Shankar	School of Information and Communication Studies, University College Dublin
Marta Sienkiewicz	CWTS, Leiden University
Markus Stocker	Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology and Leibniz University Hannover
Andrew Treloar	Australian Research Data Commons
Jonathan Zurbach	Avignon University

Workshop Programme

Preparations and programme Lorentz Workshop on Knowledge Infrastructures 15-19 April 2024

Preparations for workshop

Read all participants' statements ahead of the workshop, which will be made available to you after the submission deadline.

You might also enjoy some podcast walks (add your favourites to this list!)

- Philosophy, Guest Lisa Herzog, author of *Citizen Knowledge: Markets, Experts, and the Infrastructure of Democracy*, <https://megaphone.link/NBNK1783160197>
- The Mental Elf, C Borgman and I Pasquetto, on *Data Sharing* https://soundcloud.com/national-elf-service/christine-borgman-irene-pasquetto-data-science?in=national-elf-service/sets/cochrane-for-all&utm_source=clipboard&utm_medium=text&utm_campaign=social_sharing
- Andriola, T., & Borgman, C. L. (2023). *Decoding Data and the Future of Human Knowledge* [Podcast]. <https://digitalsquared.buzzsprout.com/2015343/14014549-decoding-data-and-the-future-of-human-knowledge>
- ...[please add here!]

Types of sessions during the workshop

-Looking at a case sessions: connect topic of the day to the case

-Knowledge sharing session to share expertise and experience (in different formats: duo lectures, short pitches, Ask-me-anything)

-Reflection session: for making connections, discussing specific issues and consolidating insights

-Working sessions on challenges for research, an agenda-setting publication (research)

-Working sessions on challenges for policy, feeding the white paper (policy)

-Walk and talk sessions to enable more open exchanges on emerging topics, with alternative for less mobile participants

-Open slot to be determined at workshop: to ensure flexibility and time for topics or issues that arise

time	Monday	Tuesday	Wednesday	Thursday	Friday
<i>Topic of the day</i>	<i>New values and emerging KI</i>	<i>Current Issues in KI assessment & policy</i>	<i>Aligning KI to new aspirations for research, evaluation and policy</i>	<i>Aligning KI to new aspirations for research, evaluation and policy</i>	<i>Agenda-setting: Towards proposals for research, policy and assessment</i>
<i>Facilitator for the day</i>	<i>Kathleen Gregory</i>	<i>Anne Beaulieu</i>	<i>Matt Mayernik</i>	<i>Sarah de Rijcke + Louise Bezuidenhout</i>	<i>Katja Mayer</i>
9.15	Arrival and welcome & registration, coffee	<p>Knowledge exchange <i>Challenges in Developing and Assessing KIs</i></p> <p>Sarah de Rijcke <i>Valuing and evaluating KIs beyond comparison</i></p> <p>Matthew Mayernik, <i>Evaluating KI via persistent identifiers: Conceptual and practical challenges</i></p>	<p>Knowledge exchange <i>Responsible Research and Data Equity</i></p> <p>Katja Mayer, <i>Differential Data Equity: Observations on Infrastructuring Participation in Citizen Social Science</i></p> <p>Irene Paschetto, <i>Science Opposition Infrastructures</i></p>	<p>Knowledge exchange <i>'Better' infrastructures and inter-infrastructural relations</i></p> <p>Malcolm Campbell-Verduyn, <i>De/post-growth, accessibility and authority of knowledge</i></p> <p>Anne Beaulieu, <i>Revealing relations: From authoritative knowledge to assessable knowledge</i></p>	<p>Writing and consolidation session for report - Zotero library</p> <p>-organisers will provide a TOC and we will divide up the sections amongst all participants</p>
10.00	Welcome from Lorentz Centre				

10.30	[continue, no break] Round of introductions Ice-breaker—mingling activity Setting up the work to be done and introduction of themes	Coffee break	Coffee break	Coffee break	Coffee break
11.00-12.00		Looking at a case RIVM	Looking at a case Open Research Knowledge Graph (ORKG)	Parallel sessions work out idea based on ideas identified on Thursday	Wrap up session 1. Overview of next steps for each group a. ch breakout group reports back 2. Reflection/evaluation of workshop What worked for you this week? What could be improved? (talk in plenary and/or write in document day 5 in google drive) 3. Further steps with/for network of people at workshop and beyond
12.00-13.30	lunch	lunch at 12:30	lunch	lunch	Lunch—end of workshop
13.30-15.00	Looking at a case ODISSEI	Travel to Amsterdam Taxi and/or cycle to station	Report back on our def of success— Best practices and challenges—small group	work on outline based on ideas identified on Thursday	

			<p>sessions with reps from cases</p> <p>Opportunity for the cases to have for further feedback And for people to practice giving their insights in a way that is useful Anything that didn't get discussed yet</p>		
15.00-15.30	Coffee break	<p>Event at IAS, co-organised with DSC 15.00-17.00 https://docs.google.com/document/d/1JAxEu9sg-Y57Dgsc3aDXqDe45</p>	<p>Coffee break from 14.30 to 15.30</p> <p>working break: please share on the board what you see as important topic</p>	Coffee break	

15.30-17.00	<p>Knowledge exchange: <i>Doing Infrastructures Differently</i></p> <p>Stephanie Hobbis: <i>Infrastructuring Diverse Values: Beyond State- and Capitalocentric Perspectives</i></p> <p>Jonathan Zurbach: <i>Leveraging persistent identifiers in the transition of knowledge infrastructures towards emerging values</i></p>	<p>zdNkch-/edit?usp=sharing&ouid=109314054987846157709&rtpof=true&sd=true</p> <p>Followed by reception. After the event, you are free to spend time in Amsterdam or head back to Leiden</p>	<p>Discuss what is on board for 30 minutes</p> <p>informal polling/grouping</p> <p>Followed by 60 minute in parallel sessions</p> <p>Parallel sessions further think about topics and how to address them</p> <p>assign 'who will pitch'</p>	<p>Plenary sessions Present work so far (outlines) From different writing groups</p>	
17.00-18.00	Welcome reception		<p>Pitch the ideas, highlighting most important points (all groups!)</p> <p>Plenary discussions of audiences: who needs to hear about each of these ideas</p>	<p>Walk and talk</p> <p>organisers to work on TOC and take stock</p>	

18:00		Free time/Informal dinner in Amsterdam	Workshop dinner: Zilt aan Zee, transportation is arranged by Lorentz Center https://ziltaanzee.nl/		
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Illustrating a knowledge infrastructure

Source: Campbell-Verduyn, M. and Hütten, M., 2023. Locating infrastructural agency: Computer protocols at the finance/security nexus. *Security Dialogue*, 54(5), pp.455-474.

"knowledge infrastructure", KI Department U. of Groningen

In this approach to visualising KIs, the lines show that not only the different stacks are important. It also shows the pathways horizontally and vertically so that the knowledge infrastructures between them become visible.

<https://xkcd.com/2347/> Dependency

Scientific Organizers

- Anne Beaulieu, University of Groningen
- Christine Borgman, University of California, Los Angeles
- Sarah de Rijcke, Leiden University
- Kathleen Gregory, Leiden University
- Matthew Mayernik, University Corporation for Atmospheric Research, NSF

Topics

- Infrastructures for Innovative Forms of Knowledge Production
- Design of Evaluation Practices
- Epistemic Diversity, Democratisation and Participation
- Techniques of Assessment
- Benchmarking, Metrics, and Rankings
- Comparison and Heterogeneity

The Lorentz Center organizes international workshops for researchers in all scientific disciplines. Its aim is to create an atmosphere that fosters collaborative work, discussions and interactions. For registration see: www.lorentzcenter.nl

Knowledge infrastructures are layered, spread out significant networks, and sometimes fuse, form bridges or fragment. Just like mushrooms. Photo by Damir Omerovic. Poster design: SuperNova Studios .NL